

SIMILARITIES AND DIFFERENCES OF VERB ASPECTS IN RUSSIAN AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES

Alisherbek Abdirasulov

Navoiy State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17785631>

Annotation. By researching the Verb and its structure in both English and Russian languages, it can be discovered that either has some similarities and differences this article aims to explore the perspectives of both English and Russian scholars on this linguistic phenomenon. Furthermore, this article gives you complete explanation about verb aspects in both languages. Understanding the comparative mechanisms in different languages is essential for linguists, educators and learners to enhance language acquisition and cross-linguistic understanding.

Key words: comparative mechanisms, cross-linguistic, english, russian.

Аннотация. Исследуя глагол и его структуру как в английском, так и в русском языках, можно обнаружить, что у каждого из них есть некоторые сходства и различия; эта статья направлена на изучение точек зрения как английских, так и русских ученых на это лингвистическое явление. Кроме того, эта статья дает вам полное объяснение аспектов глагола в обоих языках. Понимание сравнительных механизмов в разных языках необходимо для лингвистов, педагогов и учащихся для улучшения усвоения языка и межъязыкового понимания.

Ключевые слова: сравнительные механизмы, межъязыковой, английский, русский.

Annotatsiya. Ingliz va rus tillarida fe'l va uning tuzilishini o'rganib chiqib, uning o'xshashliklari va farqlari borligini aniqlash mumkin, bu maqola ingliz va rus olimlarining ushbu lingvistik hodisaga nisbatan qarashlarini o'rganishga qaratilgan. Bundan tashqari, ushbu maqola sizga ikkala tildagi fe'l jihatlarini haqida to'liq tushuntirish beradi. Turli tillardagi qiyosiy mexanizmlarni tushunish tilshunoslar, o'qituvchilar va o'quvchilar uchun tilni o'zlashtirish va tillararo tushunishni kuchaytirish uchun juda muhimdir.

Kalit so'zlar: Qiyosiy mexanizmlar, tillararo, ingliz, rus.

While English has twelve verb tenses, Russian only has three. English has no verb aspects, while Russian has two. So, while it would be awesome to have a math like equation for the perfect translation. With the verb tenses, it just isn't that simple what you can compare, however, are the functions for the different English verb tenses and Russian verb aspects. The way nailing Russian verbal aspects is memorizing these functions, and what helped me immensely to do this was recognizing patterns in English grammar of those same functions¹.

1. “I read books - я читаю книгу”² (present simple = present imperfective)
2. “I am reading a book – я читаю книгу”² (present continues = present imperfective)
3. “I have read that book – я прочитал ту книгу”² (present perfect = past perfective).
4. “I have been reading this book for several months – я читаю эту книгу уже несколько месяцев”² (Present Perfect continues = present imperfect)
5. “I read a book on the train – Я читала книгу в поезде” (Past simple = past imperfective)².
6. “I was reading a book on the train – я читала книгу в поезде” (past continues = past imperfective)².

7. “I had read the entire book before the conductor checked my ticket – я прочитала всю книгу, до того, как билет” (past perfect + past simple = past perfective + past perfective)²

Conclusion: As we can see that verb aspects in both languages vary with each other, and below, there is given obvious examples for it. However, it has some similarities like sentence structure.

REFERENCES

1. Master Russian – Usage of Russian
2. Examples: “New Girl on the Bloc” website.